

187°–188°), while elution with chloroform afforded seselin (m.p. 119°–120°) and isopimpinellin (m.p. 151°–153°). Those were also identified by m.m.p. and Co-T.L.C. with authentic specimens of the respective compounds.

The neutral part of the above extract (1.8%) on saponification, steam-distillation and repeated chromatography (alumina) yielded three products: A, B and C. Elution with petrol (40°–60°) gave a colourless product A, m.p. 68°–70°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBR}}$ 2900, 2830, 1470, 1375, 720 and 710 cm^{-1} . For final confirmation the product was subjected to G.L.C. analysis. It was thereafter found to be a mixture of *n*-alkanes composed of the series C_{23} – C_{35} ; mainly:

Heptacosane (C_{27} , 6.4%); Triacontane (C_{30} , 3.3%); Octacosane (C_{28} , 3.3%); Hentriacontane (C_{31} , 24.8%); Nonacosane (C_{29} , 41.2%); Tritriacontane (C_{33} , 16.9%).

accompanied by minor quantities of dotriacontane and pentatriacontane along with traces of the rest. The result confirms the general findings⁶ that the odd numbered alkanes predominate in plants.

Elution with petrol- C_6H_6 (1 : 1) and crystallisation from MeOH-CHCl_3 gave a crystalline solid (B, T.L.C.-homogeneous) giving positive Liebermann-Burchard and tetranitromethane tests; m.p. 137°–138°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} -33^\circ$; ν_{max} 3570 and 1653 cm^{-1} ; acetate, m.p. 126°–127°. This was identified as β -sitosterol by m.p., m.m.p., Co-T.L.C. and superimposable I.R. spectra. The acetate also did not show any depression in m.m.p. with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate.

Further elution with benzene afforded another compound (C, T.L.C./adsorbent silicagel AgNO_3 -homogeneous), m.p. 153°–155°, $[\alpha]_D +30^\circ$; M^+ 412, also giving positive Liebermann-Burchard test and yellow colour with T.N.M. It gave an acetate (T.L.C./adsorbent AgNO_3 -homogeneous), m.p. 135°–138°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} +20^\circ$; a benzoate, m.p. 160°–163°, and the 3,5-dinitrobenzoate, m.p. 231°–233° (Found: N, 4.07%; Calc. for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2$: N, 4.62%). On further investigations and comparison of the data with literature it has been found to be a new sterol, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ (Found: C, 48.00%; H, 11.89%; Calc. C, 84.40%; H, 11.72%), and has been designated as 'Indosterol'. It contains two double bonds and three vinylic protons, and belongs to stigmastane series. On the basis of various physico-chemical studies it has been assigned the structure (I) carrying a significant feature: C_{9-11} ethylenic linkage. The neutral

part indicated the presence of campesterol also by G.L.C. analysis. The benzene extract of the seeds also yielded the above coumarins and the sterols.

The alcoholic extract of the seeds was treated in three different manners and thereafter tested for the

identification of sugars, amino-acids and carboxylic acids by co-paper chromatography⁷. The results indicated the presence of glucose, rhamnose; alanine, leucine, serine, valine, asparagine, threonine; and citric, succinic and oxalic acids.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. W. Rahman, Head, Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, for facilities, and to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance to one of us (N.L.G.). Prof. M. Streibl, Prague, and Dr. R. P. Rastogi, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, are also gratefully thanked respectively for G.L.C. analyses and various spectral data.

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Hydrazone and Pyrazoline Derivatives from Mesityl Oxide

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Manuscript received 27 February 1974; revised 1 August 1974; accepted 6 August 1974

THE phenylhydrazone of mesityl oxide—an α , β -unsaturated ketone has not yet been isolated although the pyrazoline from it has been obtained. Auwers and Kreuder¹ have isolated the *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone and have cyclised it to the pyrazoline using hot acetic acid, a known reagent for the conversion of hydrazones to pyrazolines². The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of mesityl oxide although easily prepared³⁻⁵ had not been cyclised. The

cyclisation has been now effected by modifying the method.

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of mesityl oxide dissolved in acetic acid was refluxed but failed to yield the cyclised product. On using a solution of sulphuric acid in acetic acid and subsequently boiling the compound obtained was found to be the pyrazoline derivative. This was also obtained by boiling in ethanol a mixture of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, mesityl oxide and sulphuric acid.

Evidence for the cyclisation is as follows: Chemical tests viz., the Knorr colour test⁶ failed to give the expected colours but is known to fail^{1,7}, and reduction with sodium-amalgam/ethanol⁸⁻¹⁰ could not be carried out due to insolubility of the compound. Hence in spectral analyses the N-H stretch absorption peak in the I.R. region is the only conclusive evidence that could be used to distinguish the pyrazoline derivative from the hydrazone¹⁰. The I.R. spectra of this product shows no absorption band around the frequency 3000 cm^{-1} i.e., the N-H group is absent and therefore cyclisation has taken place.

Experimental

The preparation of 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-2-pyrazoline has been carried out in two ways:

(a) Cyclisation of the hydrazone to the pyrazoline:

To 0.5 g. of the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of mesityl oxide was added 15 ml of glacial acetic acid and 0.4 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid, also 2-3 drops of water. This was refluxed for 3 hrs. On cooling the compound obtained was washed with water and leached with boiling alcohol. Recrystallised from glacial AcOH. M.p. 295°.

(b) Direct preparation of the pyrazoline from 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine:

One gram of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine was dissolved in EtOH (100 ml). To this was added 5 ml of mesityl oxide and 2.0 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 . It was refluxed vigorously for 5-6 hrs. This was allowed to cool and filtered, the residue was washed successively with hot water, hot acetone and hot alcohol. Recrystallised from pure AcOH. Orange red crystals. M.p. 295°.

This compound was found to be insoluble in ethanol, acetone, ether, benzene, dioxane and water.

Analysis: $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$

	%C	%H	%N
Requires	51.99	4.69	20.21
Found	52.07	4.83	20.17

3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-2-pyrazoline.

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Studies on Emulsions of Dichlorodiphenyl trichloroethane (D.D.T.) in presence of Some Adjuvants

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Manuscript received 18 February 1974; revised 8 August 1974; accepted 14 August 1974

IN continuation with the previous work^{7,8} on the stability coefficients of emulsions of insecticides and fungicides, it was considered desirable and useful to extend the study to Dichlorodiphenyl trichloroethane $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{Cl}_5$ (commonly nicknamed D.D.T.) which has been used as insecticide within recent years. It is of outstanding effectiveness against the Japanese beetle, codling moth etc.

Kennedy³ showed that mosquitoes are repelled by the effect of contacting D.D.T. treated surfaces. Having a low melting point D.D.T. itself can not be made into a fine powder for mixture directly with a dust diluent. The best way of its use as a spray is in the form of emulsion.

Experimental

The gums were purified by the methods as described by Mukherjee and Shukla⁴ in their earlier work on gums. The emulsions were prepared at 30° by King and Mukherjee's¹ method using fixed concentration of D.D.T. alone and then by adding fixed amounts of gums, china-clay, Fuller's earth and sodium oleate keeping the ratio of the oil (kerosene or olive oil) to water as 20 : 80 so that the emulsions produced were not very viscous and could be sprayed easily for practical purposes. The size frequency analysis was done immediately and on regular intervals of time of the ageing emulsions. The stability coefficients were computed from the data on specific surfaces of these emulsions applying the theory of least squares as described by Mukherjee and Shukla^{5,6}. Emulsion type (o/w or w/o) was determined by the dye solubility method². It was found that all emulsions produced were of o/w type.